

INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY AND COMPETITIVENESS OF ORGANIC CROP BREEDING (ECOBREED) – The potato case

Peter Dolničar¹, Vladimir Meglič¹

¹Agricultural Institute of Slovenia, Hacquetova ulica 17, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

E-mail address: peter.dolnicar@kis.si

Abstract:

ECOBREED (<http://ecobreed.eu/>) is EU H2020 project performed by 25 partners organizations, with the aim of improving the availability of seed and varieties suitable for organic and low- input production. Activities are focusing on four crop species, selected for their potential contribution to increase competitiveness of the organic sector, i.e. common wheat, potato, soybean and common buckwheat. Within the project new methods, strategies and infrastructures for organic breeding, varieties with improved stress resistance, resource use efficiency and quality and improved methods for the production of high quality organic seed will be developed. The objectives of the project are: to increase the availability of seeds and varieties for the organic and low-input sector, to identify traits and combinations of traits suited to organic and low-input production environment including high nutrient use efficiency and weed competitiveness/allelopathy, to increase breeding activities for organic and low-input crop production. Ecobreed will increase the competitiveness of the organic and low-input breeding and farming sectors by identifying genetic and phenotypic variation in morphological, abiotic/biotic tolerance/resistance and nutritional quality traits that can be used in organic breeding, evaluation of the potential of genetic variation for enhanced nutrient acquisition, evaluation of the potential for increased weed competitiveness and control, optimisation of seed production/multiplication via improved agronomic and seed treatment protocols, developing efficient, ready-to-use farmer participatory breeding systems, pre-breeding of elite varieties for improved agronomic performance, biotic/abiotic stress resistance/tolerance and nutritional quality, development of training programmes in (a) genomic tools/techniques,

The main tasks of potato research within the ECOBREED project are:

- a) Screening genetic resources and breeding materials - to perform a detailed phenotypic analysis of the potato core collection of 65 cultivars identifying traits suited to organic potato production systems. High throughput phenotyping will be performed,
- b) AMF-compatibility screening,
- c) Improving seed tuber quality and vigor of organic ware and seed potato production via the use of cover crops,
- d) Colorado potato beetle and wireworm control strategies,
- e) Marker assisted selection in potato breeding - production of new potato cultivars and breeding materials suitable for organic production,
- f) Production of elite varieties and superior breeding lines with – pyramiding of *R* genes for durable field resistance to multiple *P. infestans* races and Potato virus Y (PVY).

Key words: organic potato, phenotypization, resistance breeding, PVY, late blight

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